

Reinterpreting Social Distancing as Responsibility Anchored in Social Solidarity

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In his message during *Urbi et Orbi* on 27 March 2020, Pope Francis said that the coronavirus pandemic has made us realize that “all of us fragile and disoriented, but at the same time important and needed, all of us called to row together, each of us in need of comforting the other” (Pope Francis, 2020). During this experience of helplessness, the Lord “invites us to reawaken and put into practice that solidarity and hope capable of giving strength, support and meaning to these hours when everything seems to be floundering” (Pope Francis, 2020). Social solidarity is what is called for at a time when we are morally obliged to practice social distancing. Strange and paradoxical as it may seem, social solidarity and social distancing are two sides of the same coin.

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Solidarity with the Other

Social solidarity begins with the recognition of the other—the other for whom I am responsible as Levinas would say. At the heart of Levinas’ philosophy is the encounter with the Other. For him, human person can fulfil his or her vocation only by leaving his or her self and by the act of entering into relation with the unassimilable otherness of the other. Levinas underlines the self-disinterested character of this relationship,

guided by the need and expectations of the Other. In order to become a subject, the self must accept to be responsible. And as the existence of the subject can only be justified by the Other, this responsibility is what the self assumes for the Other. “Since the Other looks at me, I am responsible for him, without even having taken on responsibilities in his regard; his responsibility is incumbent on me” (Levinas, 1985). For Levinas, the dignity of human person consists above all in this non-transferable responsibility which, in extreme cases, can go as far as shaping the destiny of the Other. He understands the ultimate social relationship as care for the Other, as unconditional responsibility assumed for the Other and as immense solidarity. This solidarity does not crush the human self; on the contrary, it is through this immense solidarity that the human subject appears in his or her irreducible singularity.

Greed for Profit

Unfortunately, driven by the greed of profit, the contemporary society has defied the value of solidarity. Once again Pope Francis succinctly sums up the contemporary lifestyle in the following words: “Greedy for profit, we let ourselves get caught up in things, and lured away by haste... we were not shaken awake by wars or injustice across the world, nor did we listen to the cry of the poor or of our ailing planet.”

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Why and in the name of what, today in the face of a pandemic, should we feel responsible for others and express solidarity with others if we accepted individualism and the “crisis of the social bond” as inevitable in our pursuit of individualistic dreams? In his 1992 essay, the French Philosopher, Gills Lipovetsky warns us that today's society is has opted for a culture promoting hedonistic norms of well-being. Sadly, this is a shared experience of all of us and it paves way for social discrimination. I was appalled by a cartoon in one of the dailies that subtly justified the practice of “untouchability” as a traditional form of wisdom to exercise social distancing. Shameful and dreadful! This is the reason why we need to interpret social distancing as a moral responsibility demanded in the name of social solidarity.

“Since the Other looks at me, I am responsible for him, without even having taken on responsibilities in his regard; his responsibility is incumbent on me.” -E Levinas

Philosophers have attempted to characterize responsibility. Their effort, far from being located in the abstract universe of ideas, comes from a situation similar to ours in the context of existential crisis. We shall retain three main features in which we shall recognize some major axes of contemporary identity.

Some Major Axes of Identity

1. Willingness: This is the normative meaning of responsibility mentioned by the well-known contemporary thinker, Paul Ricœur (1992), relating responsibility to an action done voluntarily whose consequences can be anticipated. In our present-day scenario, the challenge is to voluntarily choose to give up the pleasures of socializing that may put others' lives in

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peril. Called to practice social distancing is not primarily to protect oneself (though it is not excluded), but to ensure that we do not become carriers of corona virus (covid-19) without even being aware of it as many of us may be asymptomatic of infection. We do not mean to say here that external determinations do not exist, nor do we say that others do not have intelligence to protect themselves, but we voluntarily assume our responsibility for others. This is why certain external determinations or constraints can be silenced so that every individual may assume responsibility for the health of others. Assuming responsibility happens voluntarily or willingly and it is with this sense of freedom that our indebtedness to others is offered as a precious gift in this crucial time of pandemic.

2. Fragility: If we can take home a singular narrative from this experience of threatened by pandemic, it is that we humans are fragile and vulnerable despite our pseudo claims on “false and superfluous certainties around which we have constructed our daily schedules, our projects, our habits and priorities” (Pope Francis, 2020). It is true that all of us are in the same boat threatened by the tempest of corona pandemic, but there are some who are more fragile and vulnerable than the rest of us. Among such people are the economically poor, migrant daily wage labourers, slum dwellers, displaced refugees, the socially discriminated and politically oppressed. Sadly, in India such groups of people are not only humiliated but also despised. Tons of criticism are levelled against the mass exodus of migrant workers without remorse as though they put our lives at risk. False propaganda is relentlessly spread on social media against certain members of a particular religion as though they strategically planned the spread of corona virus. It is time we realized that we are more responsible for these vulnerable people. This is not the time for political squandering and demeaning divisiveness. According to Ricœur (1992), the term responsibility has taken on the meaning of ensuring the dignity of the other. Once again, this form of responsibility can be realized through socially distancing ourselves from narrow confines of class,

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caste and creed divisions, from condescending false propaganda and from belittling the more vulnerable population with unfounded criticisms. Our own experience of fragility has to foster in us a sense of solidarity with others who are even more fragile than we are.

3. Proximity: The French philosopher of Lithuanian Jewish ancestry, Emmanuel Levinas (1985) highlighted this by stating that responsibility arises from the face to face encounter with the other and the ethical challenge posed to the self by the face of the other who is dependent and suffering. This can be understood in the present-day context in two ways. First, it is a moment of grace when we can recognize how much we owe to our families. We can be proximate to our kith and kin who need us always and more so at this time when they may be going through emotional distress and spiritual despair. We who have set wrong priorities of placing wealth over relationship can come to reckon with the fact that what matters ultimately is those who care for us and those whom we care about. Confining ourselves to our homes enables us to rediscover the importance of proximity to our family members coupled our responsibility for them. Secondly it is a moment of recognizing our bonding with the larger human family. Living the experience of interdependence is precisely part of the destiny of being human. Thanks to frontline medical professionals, public service personnel, police officers, and

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Government administrative professionals, we are able to witness the nobility of being proximate to those who are infected with this deadly virus manifesting silently or overtly their dependence on us. Such experience of interdependence is singular, charged with affect and is dense among those who cater to the needs of the suffering other.

Conclusion

We could add to this triple characterization of the contemporary experience of responsibility another theme, which to some

extent echoes Pope Francis' appeal to care for our common home and all species inhabiting it. Jonas (1985) is concerned about the generations to come that they may inherit nature in pristine purity. Contemporary society faces unprecedented risks and new threats. Already in 1999, German social scientist, Ulrich Beck, raised the question of the risks arising from the science-technology duo. In the same vein, we can think of the social risk represented in contemporary society imbued with consumeristic lifestyle and a total disregard for poverty structurally sustained. Amidst gloom, there is a ray of hope that we are capable of alternate lifestyle without polluting our common home with the emission of excessive carbon dioxide generated by fuel consumption of vehicles, without contaminating the water sources and vast oceans, thus letting the birds sing, dolphins dance and other mammals breathe freedom. Like other viruses before, we shall withstand the brutal hold of corona virus over us, but what is important is to pledge that our sense of responsibility for others – human and other species – be anchored in the experience of solidarity that would not fade away with the extinction of corona virus.

Reference

- Beck, Ulrich (1999). *World Risk Society*. Cambridge: Polity Press.
- Jonas, Hans (1985). *The Imperative of Responsibility: In Search of an Ethics for the Technological Age*. Chicago: University of Chicago Press.
- Levinas, Emmanuel (1985). *Ethics and Infinity: Conversations with Philippe Nemo*. Trans. Richard A. Cohen. Pittsburg: Duquesne University Press.
- Lipovetsky, Gilles (1992). *Le Crépuscule du devoir : l'éthique indolore des nouveaux temps*. Paris : Gallimard.
- Pope Francis (2020, March 27). "Pope at *Urbi et orbi*: Full text of his meditation". *Vatican News*. <https://www.vaticannews.va/en/pope/news/2020-03/urbi-et-orbi-pope-coronavirus-prayer-blessing.html>
- Ricoeur, Paul (1992). "The concept of responsibility: an essay in semantic analysis" in *The Just*. Trans. David Pellauer. Chicago: University of Chicago Press.